

RESPONSE OF DIFFERENT TRAINING SYSTEMS AND SPACING LEVELS ON BENEFIT: COST RATIO OF TOMATO
(*SOLANUM LYCOPERSICUM* L.) UNDER CONTROLLED CONDITIONS.

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(MS Received: 18.01.2023; MS Revised:18.02.2023; MS Accepted: 19.03.2023)

MS 2998

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE.)

Abstract

The present study entitled the effect of different training systems and spacing levels on growth, yield and quality of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) under protected conditions was conducted in the year 2021 at Eternal University, Baru Sahib. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design with three replications and nine treatment combinations. There were three different training systems (single stem, two stem and four stem) and three spacing (45 × 30 cm, levels. (45 × 60 cm) and (45 × 90 cm). The results revealed that treatment with four stem training system and wider spacing recorded the maximum Benefit: cost ratio with high yield and good quality.

Keywords: Benefit, Cost, Spacing, Training, Tomato

Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) belongs to Solanaceae family having more than 3000 species with origin in both new and old world (Knapp, 2002). It has chromosome number of 2n=24. It is a warm season crop. Best fruit characters are obtained at temperature of 21-24°C while the temperature above 32°C adversely affects the fruit set and development.

Tomato has wider adaptation and higher yield potential. It is one of the major vegetable from India. Major tomato producing states are Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Odisha. Tomato is one of the most popular and widely consumed crops with an annual production in world approaching 130 million tons. In world, the area under tomato production is 5030545 (000 ha) with production of 180766329 (000MT) and productivity of 359337 tons/ha. The area under tomato production in India is 781 (000 ha) with production of 19007 (000 MT) and productivity of 243367 tons/ha (FAO, 2019).

In Himachal Pradesh, Tomato is grown as an off season vegetable and exported to bigger markets located at cities which brings the high returns to the farmers. Unpredictable weather followed by fluctuating temperature is a common problem in hilly areas of Himachal Pradesh which not only affects the quality and quantity of crops under open field conditions but also reduces the benefit to farmers. So, in such circumstances, cultivation of Tomato under protected conditions can play an important role in production of better quality and higher production of fruits than in the open field conditions.

Under protected conditions plant geometry is an important factor for optimum plant stand and to get maximum benefits in an area; training maximizes the plant availability to obtain the light needed for the improved growth and development (Guo et al. 1991) The greatest function of leaf and fruit pruning in vegetable production is to provide a balance between vegetative and reproductive growth balance (Seniz et al. 2000).

In greenhouse tomato production, spacing is an important component in tomato production. Optimum spacing enhances the yield and quality of tomato. Plant spacing plays a critical role in minimizing diseases in organic vegetable culture under greenhouse conditions. It changes the air movements around the plant rows and thus changes the relative humidity levels. They also influence the light received by plant canopy, plant growth duration, yield and quality (Saka et al. 2013).

Material and Methods

The experiment was conducted in randomized block design of 1.5×1m plots of nine treatment combinations, under naturally ventilated polyhouse at experimental research farm of Eternal University, Baru Sahib, Distt. Sirmaur, Himachal Pradesh. The HeemSohna variety was planted in different treatment combinations constituted with three spacing levels (S₁ - 45×30 cm, S₂ - 45×60 cm and S₃ - 45×90 cm) and three training levels viz. T₁ - single stem, T₂ - double stem and T₃ - four stem. Fertilizer (Polyfeed 19:19:19) was used twice a week. The details of the treatment combinations are given in table no.1

Table No.1 Details of treatment combinations-

Treatment Combinations	Training	Spacing (cm)
T ₁ S ₁	T ₁ = 1 Stem	S ₁ = 45×30cm
T ₂ S ₁	T ₂ = 2 Stem	S ₁ = 45×30cm
T ₃ S ₁	T ₃ = 4 Stem	S ₁ = 45×30cm
T ₂ S ₂	T ₂ = 2 Stem	S ₂ = 45×60cm
T ₃ S ₂	T ₃ = 4 Stem	S ₂ = 45×60cm
T ₁ S ₂	T ₁ = 1 Stem	S ₂ = 45×60cm
T ₃ S ₃	T ₃ = 4 Stem	S ₃ = 45×90cm
T ₁ S ₃	T ₁ = 1 Stem	S ₃ = 45×90cm
T ₂ S ₃	T ₂ = 2 Stem	S ₃ = 45×90cm

Results and Discussion

This aspect of cost analysis is calculated for benefit cost ratio in which we get to know the profit or loss we get from our investigation.

Total Fixed Cost

Total fixed costs are the sum of all the consistent expenses a person must pay. It consists of cost of land (Rs.2500 per treatment), maintenance cost (Rs.125 per treatment) and fixed cost (Rs.2625 per treatment) which leads to total fixed cost (Rs.23625). These prices are fixed for a given season and not changed due to fluctuations in market conditions.

Total Variable Cost

The total variable cost consists of different components which are being required during cultivating the crop. The prices of these variables vary with the market conditions and these play a major role in selling price of a crop and ultimately benefit cost ratio is affected. The different components which affected the variable cost in the present experiment along with the values were- Cost of seed- (Rs.349.92), electricity (Rs.2999.97), labor (Rs.54000), fertilizer (Rs.13500), plant protection (Rs.3499.92), staking threads (Rs.450) that lead to variable cost (Rs.8311.09) per treatment ultimately leading to a total variable cost (Rs.74799.81) during the entire experiment.

Table No.2 Total Cost Price and Total Selling Price

Treatment Combinations	Total cost price			Total selling price		
	Fixed cost (Rs)	Variable cost (Rs)	Total cost (Rs)	Yield (Kg)	Rate /kg	Total (Rs)
T ₁ S ₁	2625	8311.09	10936.09	930.63	40	37225.33
T ₂ S ₁	2625	8311.09	10936.09	1157.40	40	46296.13
T ₃ S ₁	2625	8311.09	10936.09	1537.62	40	61504.89
T ₂ S ₂	2625	8311.09	10936.09	1773.07	40	70922.67
T ₃ S ₂	2625	8311.09	10936.09	1901.37	40	76055.00
T ₁ S ₂	2625	8311.09	10936.09	1677.30	40	67092.09
T ₃ S ₃	2625	8311.09	10936.09	2827.51	40	113100.44
T ₁ S ₃	2625	8311.09	10936.09	1718.39	40	68735.73
T ₂ S ₃	2625	8311.09	10936.09	1965.60	40	78624.11
Total	23625.00	74799.81	98424.81	15488.91	360.00	619556.39

Benefit Cost Ratio

Benefit cost ratio is the most important component. It is calculated by dividing the benefit with cost price. Among the different treatment combinations T₃S₃ recorded maximum of Rs102164.35 which recorded a benefit cost ratio 9.34.

The maximum B.C ratio was recorded in plants trained with four stem and placed at wider spacing because this treatment combination

recorded the best quality fruits along with maximum yield that fetched maximum price in the market. There was minimum incidence of pests and disease in this combination resulting in production of maximum marketable fruits which fetches maximum benefit and consequently maximum B.C ratio.

Table No.3 Benefit Cost Ratio-

Treatment Combinations	Total Cost price (Rs.)	Total Selling price (Rs.)	Benefit	B:C Ratio
T ₁ S ₁	10936.09	37225.33	26289.24	2.40
T ₂ S ₁	10936.09	46296.13	35360.04	3.23
T ₃ S ₁	10936.09	61504.89	50568.80	4.62
T ₂ S ₂	10936.09	70922.67	59986.58	5.49
T ₃ S ₂	10936.09	76055.00	65118.91	5.95
T ₁ S ₂	10936.09	67092.09	56156.00	5.13
T ₃ S ₃	10936.09	113100.44	102164.35	9.34
T ₁ S ₃	10936.09	68735.73	57799.64	5.29
T ₂ S ₃	10936.09	78624.11	67688.02	6.19

The result findings are in accordance with Mazed et al. 2015, as in his findings three stem pruning system recorded highest benefit cost ratio. Alam et al. 2016 also found maximum benefit cost ratio in plants trained with four stem. Kanwar et al. 2016 and Singh et al. 2017 found that wider spacing gave the maximum benefit returns.

Conclusion

From the present study it is concluded that interaction T₃S₃ (4stem/ 45×90 cm) recorded the maximum cost benefit ratio with higher yield, good quality fruits, less incidence of insect pests and disease. So, we can recommend the farmers to use four stem training system with wider spacing. However, the best vegetative parameters were recorded by T₁S₁ (1stem/ 45×30 cm).

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